

EFFECTIVE TEACHING AND LEARNING OF FRENCH DURING TEACHING PRACTICE EXERCISE TOWARDS SUSTAINING THE INTEREST OF LEARNERS: A STUDY OF EACOED, OYO AND KWSCE, ILORIN

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Abstract

Student teaching programme is planned to develop and evaluate student-teachers' competence in actual classroom and school settings. This study examines effective teaching and learning of French during teaching practice exercise towards sustaining the interest of learners: a study of EACOED (Emmanuel Alayande College of Education), Oyo and KWSCE (Kwara State College of Education), Ilorin. Some French student-teachers do not choose French as their teaching subject during their teaching practice exercise. They rather choose other subject or assignment with their various excuses. Some schools give other school assignments at the expense of practicing teaching in their schools. This study aims at finding the ways of sustaining the learner's interest in the class of French. It suggests that French student-teachers and other school authorities need to contribute positively to enhance and sustain the interest of students of French. It recommends that French student-teachers should teach French during teaching practice. The head teachers, Old Student Association and Parent-Teacher Association should come to the aid of French education in the provision of modern teaching materials in their various schools.

Key Words: Teaching and learning, French language, Teaching practice exercise, learner's interest and student-teacher.

Introduction

National Policy on Education made French one of the core subjects in both middle and upper Basic levels of Education. The Policy recognizes the great usefulness of French to Nigerian school pupils looking at the geographical location of the country and the enormous role played by Nigeria in the West African Sub-region and particularly in Africa (NPE 1998).

French becomes one of the twelve compulsory subjects as from Basic 4 through Basic 9. It becomes a major international language of science, commerce, industry, diplomacy and technology. It also includes the need for Nigerians to acquire competence in French (NPE 1998).

Students are to play roles expected of them by Colleges of Education and Universities since they train them to be competent French student-teachers to handle both primary and secondary schools. These institutions expose student-teachers to political and social-cultural of francophone

African people and the entire world. They form them to be competent hands to teach French in classrooms (NCCCE 2012, 2020, www.nccceonline.edu.ng). Student-teachers are expected to use their period of teaching practice towards achieving objectives of French Education curriculum. (FME 2003, Obiama, 2007).

Teaching Practice Exercise

Teaching practice is an exercise that takes place with children and within a school in which teaching and learning take place. Teaching practice exercise is an exercise in which student-teachers practice towards the attainment of the planned objectives of the policy makers.

Every student is required to participate in teaching practice exercise (www.nccceonline.edu.ng). The trainees are required to earn six (6) credits for teaching practice (www.nccceonline.edu.ng). It takes the duration of twenty-six (26) weeks and the credit earned should

be registered under EDU 311. his teaching practice takes place during first Semester in 300 Level (NCCE 2012, 2020, Aglazor, 2017). A college of education or university faculty of education teacher education programme is formed by its institution's unique vision and mission. Student practicing teaching is the most important experience in teacher education programme and is generally based on teacher preparation programme in Nigeria (www.ajol.info).

It should mandatory that student-teachers of French are supervised by the lecturers of the department of French during the teaching practice.

Tout étudiant devrait participer à un programme d'enseignement pratique pour une durée de 26 semaines et le crédit acquis devra être inscrit comme EDU 324. Cet enseignement pratique devra avoir lieu pendant le premier semestre de la troisième année (De septembre-avril) (NCCE 2020).

Adepoju, Okemakinde and Ojo (2008) saw education as a huge investment of Nigeria government. This made training of teachers become an important aspect of teaching-learning process. Their study therefore focused on how to ensure effective teaching process by ensuring a qualitative teaching practice exercise. They recommended that God should motivate both the supervisors and student-teachers so as to put in their best. The period of teaching practice for students should be extended from one term to a full academic year. Ojetunde, Salami and Adepoju (2015) reviewed how teaching practice exercise can be transformed through ethics. They saw that the supervisors and students and teachers are involved in the change. They must abide by certain ethics to facilitate quality training of teachers. They noted various lapses and shortcomings that go with teaching practice and recommended the need to for student teachers to give appropriate sanction to student and supervisor who violate any of the ethics. Akande (2021) examined the role of language student-teachers in teaching practice between Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, (EACOED) Oyo and schools of teaching practice. This helped to detect level of decrease in the relationship between the selected institution and the schools of teaching practice. The study recommended that language student-teachers should strengthen formal good relationship between both parties. There should be cordial

interaction between student-teachers and students, regular with head teachers in the school. Akande and Akinpelu (2021) investigated the view of French and English students in Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo on literary studies: A case of 200 and 300 Levels with the objectives of being creative, responsible, effective, efficient and self-reliant in their areas of specialization, adding more values to the oral and written literature they acquire in the school and reducing the high level of unemployment, terrorism, banditry and insurgency in Nigeria. This study is meant to fill the research gap by writing with the result of the findings, encouraging French student-teachers and others to stimulate and sustain the interest of every child in their various schools of practice and beyond and then translates that interest into the achievement of learning.

Statement of the Problem

Some French student-teachers do not choose French as their teaching subject during their teaching practice. Their argument is that there is no French regular teacher in the school. Students are too many to teach and I am the only student-teacher to handle French subject in the whole school. Students do not have interest in French as a subject in the school.

Ability to sustain the interest of learners has been a great problem for French student-teachers in some schools. And, this is necessary. They do not know the importance of stimulating and sustaining the interest of every child in a class. Few have an almost instinctive gift for doing this successfully right from the start but some cannot due to their lack of experience.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims at finding the ways of sustaining the learner's interest in teaching French during teaching practice by the student teachers. It gives practical guidance and encouragement to French student- teachers towards sustaining the learners' interest and translating that interest into the achievement of learning.

It is to bring out the significance of teaching the subject (French) during teaching practice instead of just teaching any other subject. This gives the researcher the image of student-teachers in their practicing schools teaching French and sustaining their learners' interest.

It is therefore prepared towards the achievement of the established objectives of French education in Middle and Upper classes in the schools by the curriculum developer as in his introduction, the Director, Curriculum Development Centre:

1. enseigner comment communiquer en français par l'emploi systématique d'une méthode appropriée e.g la méthode communicative.
 2. élargir chez les apprenants, la connaissance des cultures françaises.
 3. encourager l'enseignant à présenter la matière de façon simple afin de soutenir l'intérêt des apprenants qui sont souvent en contact avec la langue française pour la première-fois.
 4. donner envie à l'enseignant de mettre à contribution sa créativité et son imagination pour optimiser la méthodologie notamment en améliorant le matériel utilisé en classe. ... Adeniyi, NERDC, Abuja (2008); Adeniyi, (2007)
1. *To teach the learners to communicate in French Language through systematic use of appropriate methods.*
 2. *To widen the scope of the learner's knowledge about the French and the French speaking world.*
 3. *To assist the teacher in his presentation of the subject in the simplest possible manner, in order to sustain the interest of the learners who in most cases, will be coming into contact with French for the first time.*
 4. *To encourage the innovative capacity of the teacher who should be able to improve on materials in order to enhance effective delivery. ... (NERDC, 2008).*

Significance of the Study

This research study would be useful for French student-teachers in their first attempt in the field of teaching and learning in the class of French before students. Likewise other French teachers would find some significant lessons to learn towards attaining objectives of French education in schools and realizing the specific goals of education in Nigerian schools. French regular and student-teachers would note the importance of sustaining learner's interest in the class of French. French student-teachers would see the need to

teach French subject in their schools of practice. It would help them create greatest interest in it and let the educational activities be learner centered and adopt a more positive attitude towards learner's success.

This research would guide and assist student-teachers on how to handle French students in a big classroom since French is compulsory from primaries 4 to JSS III classes. They would know that it is necessary to relate French education to overall community needs. French education should be activity and ICT based. This would help other researchers fill the research gap in the nearest future.

Research Questions

This study gives answers to these three questions:

1. Do you teach French language as a subject during your teaching practice?
2. What do you do to enhance effective delivery of French in your teaching practice schools?
3. What are the efforts of the school authority towards the enhancement of French in the school?

Objectives of Teaching Practice

(NCCE, 2012, 2020) established certain sets of objectives to demonstrate that teaching practice is a mandatory component of teacher training. They are:

1. To expose student-teachers to real life classroom experiences under the supervision of professional teachers.
2. To provide the forum for student-teachers to discover their strengths and weaknesses in classroom teaching.
3. To familiarize student-teachers with real school environment as their future work place.
4. To provide student-teachers with an opportunity for further acquisition of professional skills, competence, personal characteristics and experience for full-time teaching after graduation.
5. To help student-teachers develop a positive attitude towards the teaching profession.
6. To serve as a means of assessing the quality of training being provided by teacher training institutions.

Methodology

Sample: The scope of this study consists of 35 NCE students in the Department of French who were randomly selected from 300 level students on teaching practice in Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo, Oyo State and Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin, Kwara State.

Instrumentation: Some questionnaires were administered on students to collect the data at the period of the research. It has two sections (A and B). Section A asks of the respondents' Bio-Data. Section B contains fifteen (15) items given to the respondents. The response of each respondent to question is SA. A. D. SD. SA if the respondent strongly agrees with the statement. A if He/ She agrees. D if the respondent strongly agrees and SD if strongly disagrees.

Results

Table 4.1 :Result of the respondents on the basis of School

VARIABLES	Agree responses %	Disagree responses %	Total percentage %
I teach French as a subject during my teaching practice.	15 (42.86%)	20 (57.14%)	100
I teach my other subject combination during my teaching practice.	20 (57.14%)	15 (42.86%)	100
I teach French and other subject during my teaching practice.	22 (62.86%)	13 (37.14%)	100
I act as the head teacher during my teaching practice.	5 (14.29%)	30 (85.71%)	100
I train students for inter-school sport activities during my teaching practice.	15 (42.86%)	20 (57.14%)	100

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Twelve (12) French Students of Emmanuel Alayande College of Education and twenty-three (23) from Kwara State College of Education Ilorin responded to the questionnaires due to the limited number of students in EACOED, Oyo. The researchers used simple percentage to analyze the respondents' responses.

Validation and Reliability of the Instrument

The questionnaires were given to colleagues in the Department to amend and correct some mistakes in order to render the instrument valid and reliable before reaching the respondents. Copies of the questionnaires were distributed to the respondents by French lecturers with the support of the heads of department of French in each institution and were collected immediately.

Question 2:What do you do to enhance effective delivery of French in your teaching practice schools?

Table 4.3: The contribution of the French student-teachers towards the enhancement of effective delivery of French in their school of teaching practice.

VARIABLES	Agree responses %	Disagree responses %	Total percentage %
I use different methods on different situations to teach my students.	20 (57.14%)	15 (42.86%)	35 (100)
I create some improvised audio/visual aids to teach my students/pupils.	10 (40%)	25 (60%)	35 (100)
I organize French reading club in the school of teaching practice.	5 (14.28%)	30 (85.72%)	35 (100)
I use communicative method to teach my students/pupils.	20 (57.14%)	15 (42.86%)	35 (100)
I concentrate on intelligent among the students in my teaching of French.	30 (85.72%)	5 (14.28%)	35 (100)

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Question 3:What are the efforts of the school authority towards the enhancement of effective teaching and learning of French in their school of teaching practice?

Table 4.4:The effort of the school authority towards the enhancement of effective teaching and learning of French in their school of teaching practice.

VARIABLES	Agree responses %	Disagree responses %	Total percentage %
My head of school requests for Youth Corps member in French discipline to teach students.	10 (40%)	25 (60%)	35 (100)
My head of school provides some ICT materials for teaching of French in my school.	5 (14.28%)	30 (85.72%)	35 (100)
My head of school allows students to speak French in the school premise.	15 (42.86%)	20 (57.14%)	35 (100)
My head of school sponsors students to French competition.	2 (5.71%)	33 (94.29%)	35 (100)
My head of school provides a spare room designated for French activity in my practicing school.	5 (14.28%)	30 (85.72%)	35 (100)

Source: Field Survey, 2019

Data Analysis

Table 1 gave the number of the respondents on the basis of the school; Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo and Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin. It showed the number of respondents that responded to the instrument. They were 12 (34.29%) from Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo and 23 (65.71%) from Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin.

Table 2 showed the French student-teachers' teaching subject in the school of teaching practice. It so declared that 15 (42.86%) respondents agreed that they taught French during their teaching practice whereas 20 (57.14%) of them did not agree. 20 (57.14%) affirmed they taught their other subject combination in the school of teaching practice while 15 (42.86%) disagreed. 22 (62.86%) of the respondent declared that they taught French and other subject while 13 (37.14%) disagreed.

5 (14.29%) agreed that they acted as the head teacher in their practicing school while 30 (85.71%) failed to agree with the question. 15 (42.86%) of the respondents agreed that they trained students for inter-school sport activities in the school of practice on the contrary 20 (57.14%) did not agree.

In Table 3, item 1 showed that 20 (57.14%) of the respondents use different methods on different situation in the teaching of French in their schools while 15 (42.86%) didn't. In item 2 10 (40%) agreed that they created improvised teaching technology while 25 (60%) did not create any. 5 (14.28%) of the respondents organized French reading club in the school of teaching practice whereas 30 (85.71%) did not. 20 (57.14%) used communicative method to teach their students in the school of practice whereas 15 (42.86%) did not agree with the statement. 30 (85.72%) of the respondents agreed that they concentrated on intelligent among the students in their teaching of French 5 (14.28%) did not agree.

Table 4 indicated that 10 (40%) of the respondents made request for Youth Corps member in French discipline to teach students in the practicing school while 25 (60%) did not attempt to do that. 5 (14.28%) of the respondents agreed that their head teachers provided some ICT materials for the teaching of French in their school whereas 30 (85.72%) disagreed with the statement. 15 (42.86%) of the heads of school allowed students

to speak French in the school premise while 20 (57.14%) didn't. 2 (5.71%) of the respondents confirmed that their head of schools sponsored students to French competition while 33 (94.29%) of them failed to agree with the statement. 5 (14.28%) of the respondents agreed that their heads of schools provide a spare room designated for French activity in my practicing school whereas 30 (85.72%) did not attempt to make provision for a spare room for French activity.

Discussion of the Findings

The result of the finding showed in Table 1 that the population and scope of the study were 12 (34.29%) from EACOED (Emmanuel Alayande College of Education) Oyo and 23 (65.71%) from KWSCE (Kwara State College of Education), Ilorin. This means that there is very low admission in the

selected colleges which calls for attention on the part of the school management to look into and find necessary solution to the survival of the department in colleges of education since French is one of the compulsory subjects from Primaries 4-6 and Junior Secondary School 1-111.

Table 2 showed that some French student-teachers taught French subject in their schools of teaching practice, some taught their other subject combination, some taught French and other subject, some acted as the head teacher in their practicing school and some said they trained students for inter-school sport activities in the school of practice. This result cannot render any help towards achieving the objectives of teaching practice and French education as stated earlier. It debars the effective teaching and learning of French during teaching practice exercise. Learners' interest cannot be sustained since French student-teacher is disallowed to teach her course of study 'French' for other assignment; acting head of school, sport master/mistress and so on

In Table 3, some student-teachers of French use different methods on different situation in the teaching of French in their schools while some did not, some created improvised teaching aids while other failed to do so. Very low percentage organized French reading club in the school of teaching practice whereas many of them did not know the importance of doing so. Average French

student teachers used communicative method to teach their students in the school of practice others did not. Many of them agreed that they concentrated on intelligent among the students in their teaching of French and left other students uncared. These entire wrong attitudes on the part of student teachers in French class can neither result to an effective teaching of French nor sustain learners' interest in the class.

Table 4 revealed that few heads of schools made request for Youth Corps member in French discipline to teach students in the practicing school but this does not border larger number of them. Few of these head teachers provided some ICT materials for the teaching of French in their schools while many of them are less concerned. Average of the heads of school allowed students to speak French in the school premise while some still didn't. It was also confirmed that very low number of their head of schools sponsored students to French competition while larger number were not interested. Likewise, a very low number the heads of schools provided a spare room designated for French activity in schools. This result testifies to the fact that many school heads are not in the same shoe of progress and development with the government and committees on education in the country.

Conclusion

French student-teacher must not see themselves out of the system. They can globalize and as well glocalize the new environment they find themselves by putting in all their efforts to see that they create and retain their students' interest in French education during their short term. This would surely give them long term remembrance in that school. They will be referred to as responsible educators and achievers.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made at the end of the findings:

1. French student-teachers should see the teaching of French during teaching practice very important task since practice makes perfection.
2. They should apply the various teaching methodologies they learn in the college in the teaching exercise especially the use of

communicative method of teaching. This would enable learners to have interest in the subject and express themselves in the language.

3. The head teachers should assist in the provision of ICT materials in their various schools. This would assist student-teachers make use of audio and audio-visual materials in their teaching and aid learning on the part of learners in the class.
4. The Old Student Association should provide Centre for French learning.
5. The School Parents Teacher Association need to play positive role towards the enhancement of learner's interest in French education in their schools.
6. School P.T.A. can help sponsor students on French competition. This will aid their learning and sustain their interest in French education.

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